

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340352002>

Antimicrobial properties of Echinacea purpurea

Preprint · April 2020

DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33343.05285

CITATIONS

0

READS

377

1 author:

Domina Petric

UHC Split

156 PUBLICATIONS 2 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Chasing new drugs [View project](#)

Safety in traffic. Physician's perspective [View project](#)

Antimicrobial properties of *Echinacea purpurea*

Domina Petric, MD

ABSTRACT

Considering that *Echinacea purpurea* has both antibacterial (against *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Legionella pneumophila*...) and antiviral properties (mostly against respiratory viral infections, including coronaviruses) it is suitable for relieving symptoms of respiratory tract infections.

Echinacea purpurea preparations could be also effective as prophylactic treatment for all coronaviruses, including newly occurring SARS-CoV-2.

ANTIBACTERIAL AND ANTIFUNGAL PROPERTIES

Echinacea purpurea (Asteraceae) is a perennial medicinal herb with important immunostimulatory and anti-inflammatory properties, especially the alleviation of cold symptoms.

Biological activities of the plant such as antioxidant, antibacterial, antiviral, and larvicidal activities have been reported in previous experimental studies. Different classes of secondary metabolites of the plant such as alkaloids, caffeic acid derivatives, polysaccharides, and glycoproteins are believed to be biologically and pharmacologically active¹.

The results of some studies revealed that polysaccharides from *E. purpurea* cell culture are able to provide protection against *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Candida albicans*, mainly through macrophages and polymorphonuclears in normal mice².

The extract of *E. purpurea* considerably inhibited growth of *Candida albicans* and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, but no inhibition zone was observed

for *Aspergillus niger*. The extract obtained by classical method showed higher antimicrobial activity in comparison with those obtained by ultrasound-assisted extraction³.

In another study, three pathogens *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, and *Legionella pneumophila* were sensitive to the preparation of the plant, although *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Enterococcus faecalis* (vancomycin-resistant), *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* were relatively resistant to the drug, while two fungi organisms, *C. albicans* and *Trichoderma viride*, were essentially resistant to the preparation⁴.

ANTIVIRAL PROPERTIES

Echinacea extract showed activity against respiratory viral infections (rhinoviruses, influenza viruses, respiratory syncytial virus, coronavirus, calicivirus, herpes viruses⁵).

Pleschka and coworkers (2009) found in the study that human H1N1-type IV, highly pathogenic avian IV (HPAIV) of the H5- and H7-types, as well as swine origin IV (S-OIV, H1N1), were all inactivated in cell culture assays by the *Echinacea purpurea* (Echinaforce, EF) preparation at concentrations ranging from the recommended dose for oral consumption to several orders of magnitude lower. Detailed studies with the H5N1 HPAIV strain indicated that direct contact between EF and virus was required, prior to infection, in order to obtain maximum inhibition in virus replication. Hemagglutination assays showed that the extract inhibited the receptor binding activity of the virus, suggesting that the extract interferes with the viral entry into cells. In sequential passage studies under treatment in cell culture with the H5N1 virus no EF-resistant variants emerged, in contrast to Tamiflu (oseltamivir), which produced resistant viruses upon passaging. Furthermore, the Tamiflu-resistant virus

was just as susceptible to EF as the wild type virus⁶.

The aqueous extract of *E. purpurea* were active against acyclovir-susceptible and acyclovir-resistant strains of both *herpes simplex virus 1* (HSV-1) and *herpes simplex virus 2* (HSV-2) *in vitro*⁷, whereas the hexane extract of the plant root and cichoric acid inhibited HSV-1⁸.

In addition, cichoric acid inhibited human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) integrase^{9, 10}.

ACTIVITY AGAINST CORONAVIRUSES

Signer and coworkers (2020) investigated in the study the antiviral potential of *Echinacea purpurea* (Echinaforce[®]) against human coronavirus (HCoV) 229E and the highly pathogenic MERS- and SARS-CoVs *in vitro*. They found that HCoV-229E was irreversibly inactivated when exposed to Echinaforce at 3.2µg/ml IC₅₀. Pre-treatment of cell lines did not inhibit infection with HCoV-229E and post-infection treatment had only a marginal effect on virus propagation at 50µg/ml. However, they did observe a protective effect in an organotypic respiratory cell culture system by exposing pre-treated

respiratory epithelium to droplets of HCoV-229E, imitating a natural infection. Finally, antiviral activity was not restricted to common cold coronaviruses, as the highly pathogenic SARS- and MERS-CoVs were inactivated at comparable concentrations. These results suggest that *Echinacea purpurea* preparations, such as Echinaforce, could be effective as prophylactic treatment for all CoVs, including newly occurring strains, such as SARS-CoV-2¹¹.

Echinacea might not be suitable for the patients with existing autoimmune diseases because it can contribute to an overworking immune system and cytokine storms. *Echinacea* preparations might not be suitable for the treatment of COVID-19, but only as prophylaxis¹².

CONCLUSION

Considering that *Echinacea purpurea* has both antibacterial (against *Streptococcus pyogenes*, *Haemophilus influenzae*, *Legionella pneumophila*...) and antiviral properties (mostly against respiratory viral infections, including coronaviruses) it is suitable for relieving symptoms of respiratory tract infections.

Echinacea purpurea medicinal preparations can be used for prevention, in the treatment of early phase and in mild respiratory infections as monotherapy.

Echinacea purpurea preparations could be also effective as prophylactic treatment for all coronaviruses, including newly occurring SARS-CoV-2.

Echinacea purpurea is "Erba superba" for prevention and treatment of respiratory tract infections.

REFERENCES

1. Manayi A, Vazirian M, Saeidnia S. Echinacea purpurea: Pharmacology, phytochemistry and analysis methods. *Pharmacogn Rev.* 2015;9(17):63–72.
2. Roesler J, Steinmüller C, Kiderlen A, Emmendörffer A, Wagner H, Lohmann-Matthes ML. Application of purified polysaccharides from cell cultures of the plant *Echinacea purpurea* to mice mediates protection against systemic infections with *Listeria monocytogenes* and *Candida albicans*. *Int J Immunopharmacol.* 1991; 13(1):27-37.
3. Stojicevic S, Stanisavljevic A, Velickovic D, Veljkovic V, Lazic M. Antioxidant and antimicrobial activities of *Echinacea* (*Echinacea purpurea* L.) extracts obtained by classical and ultrasound extraction. *Chin J Chem Eng.* 2009;17:478–83.
4. Sharma SM, Anderson M, Schoop SR, Hudson JB. Bactericidal and anti-inflammatory properties of a standardized *Echinacea* extract (Echinaforce): dual actions against respiratory bacteria. *Phytomedicine.* 2010;17(8-9):563-8.
5. Hudson JB. Applications of the phytomedicine *Echinacea purpurea* (Purple Coneflower) in infectious diseases. *J Biomed Biotechnol.* 2012;2012:769896.
6. Pleschka S, Stein M, Schoop R, Hudson JB. Anti-viral properties and mode of action of standardized *Echinacea purpurea* extract against highly pathogenic avian influenza virus (H5N1, H7N7) and swine-origin H1N1 (S-OIV). *Virol J.* 2009;13(6):197.
7. Thompson KD. Antiviral activity of *Viracea* against acyclovir susceptible and acyclovir resistant

strains of herpes simplex virus. *Antiviral Res.* 1998;39(1):55-61.

8. Binns SE, Hudson J, Merali S, Arnason JT. Antiviral activity of characterized extracts from echinacea spp. (Heliantheae: Asteraceae) against herpes simplex virus (HSV-1). *Planta Med.* 2002;68(9):780-3.

9. McDougall B, King PJ, Wu BW, Hostomsky Z, Reinecke MG, Robinson WE Jr. Dicafeoylquinic and dicafeoyltartaric acids are selective inhibitors of human immunodeficiency virus type 1 integrase. *Antimicrob Agents Chemother.* 1998;42(1):140-6.

10. Robinson WE Jr. L-chicoric acid, an inhibitor of human immunodeficiency virus type 1 (HIV-1) integrase, improves on the in vitro anti-HIV-1 effect of Zidovudine plus a protease inhibitor (AG1350). *Antiviral Res.* 1998;39(2):101-11.

11. Signer J, Jonsdottir HR, Albrich WC, et al. In vitro antiviral activity of Echinaforce®, an *Echinacea purpurea* preparation, against common cold coronavirus 229E and highly pathogenic MERS-CoV and SARS-CoV. *Virology.* 2020. DOI: 10.21203/rs.2.24724/v1

12. BREAKING! Coronavirus Research: Could Echinacea Act As A Prophylaxis Against The SARS-CoV-2 Coronavirus? More Research Warranted. 10-03-2020. Retrieved from (01-04-2020)

<https://www.thailandmedical.news/news/breaking-coronavirus-research-could-echinacea-act-as-a-prophylaxis-against-the-sars-cov-2-coronavirus-more-research-warranted>